

COMPARISON OF DIETARY STYLES IN DIFFERENT OBESITY PHENOTYPES**Majidov Sharifjon Xusenovich**

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Abstract. Obesity has become the most important medical and social problem today, and according to the World Health Organization, the number of patients with obesity has increased threefold from 1975 to 2016. According to the World Health Organization, 44-57% of people with overweight and obesity problems have diabetes mellitus (type II), 17-23% have coronary heart disease, 17% have arterial hypertension, 30% have gallstone disease, 14% have osteoarthritis, and 11% have malignant tumors. Etiological factors that contribute to the development of obesity include dietary disorders, physical inactivity, harmful habits (alcoholism, smoking, nicotine-containing products), and stress

Keywords: Metabolically unhealthy obesity, Metabolically healthy obesity, physical inactivity.

**СРАВНЕНИЕ СТИЛЕЙ ПИТАНИЯ ПРИ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ ФЕНОТИПАХ
ОЖИРЕНИЯ**

Аннотация. Ожирение стало важнейшей медицинской и социальной проблемой современности, и по данным Всемирной организации здравоохранения, количество пациентов с ожирением увеличилось в три раза с 1975 по 2016 год. По данным Всемирной организации здравоохранения, 44-57% людей с избыточным весом и проблемами ожирения страдают сахарным диабетом (II тип), 17-23% - ишемической болезнью сердца, 17% - артериальной гипертензией, 30% - желчнокаменной болезнью, 14% - остеоартрозом и 11% - злокачественными опухолями. К этиологическим факторам, способствующим развитию ожирения, относятся нарушения питания, физическая неактивность, вредные привычки (алкоголизм, курение, никотиносодержащие продукты) и стресс.

Ключевые слова: Метаболически нездоровое ожирение, Метаболически здоровое ожирение, физическая неактивность.

Objective: To identify the dietary differences behind metabolically healthy obesity and metabolically unhealthy obesity.

Materials and methods of the study. The study involved 40 volunteers aged 20 to 40 years with obesity and overweight problems and 10 patients with normal weight who followed a healthy lifestyle who came to the Olivai polyclinic No. 4, Bukhara city, Bukhara region for preventive examination. The group with obesity problems was divided into 18 metabolically healthy groups with one sign of metabolic syndrome and 22 metabolically unhealthy groups with two or more signs of metabolic syndrome according to the classification (NCEP ATP III (2001)).

In order to study the characteristics of nutrition, which is part of the lifestyle that plays a key role in the development of obesity, a written questionnaire was administered among them.

Ban result: The results of the survey are in the table below.

Questions	Group I Metabolically Healthy	Group II Metabolically unhealthy	Group III Control group
In what situation do you eat? -When you are hungry -When you are stressed, nervous -Always at the same time	67.7% 16.7% 27.8%	63.6% 27.2% 22.7%	90% 0 % 10%
What are your favorite sweets? -Honey -Chocolate -Pastry	33.3 % 72.2% 44.5%	18.1% 72.7% 41 %	30 % 40 % 20 %
Non-alcoholic beverages? -Coffee -Sweet carbonated drinks	61.1% 27.78%	31.8% 31.8 %	40 % 10 %
Frequency of drinking alcoholic beverages -Every week -On holidays	33.4% 38.8 %	41 % 50 %	10 % 40 %

Conclusion: When comparing the diets of metabolically healthy and metabolically unhealthy obese people, it became clear that overweight people eat not when they are hungry, but when they are stressed, consuming large amounts of sweets, carbonated drinks and alcohol. This leads to metabolically unhealthy obesity. The main factor in the development of obesity in patients is psycho-emotional disorders and stress.

REFERENCES

1. Saodat, A., Vohid, A., Ravshan, N., & Shamshod, A. (2020). MRI study in patients with idiopathic coxarthrosis of the hip joint. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(2), 410-415.
2. Axmedov, S. J. (2023). EFFECTS OF THE DRUG MILDRONATE. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(20), 40-59.
3. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). ASCORBIC ACID: ITS ROLE IN IMMUNE SYSTEM, CHRONIC INFLAMMATION DISEASES AND ON THE ANTIOXIDANT EFFECTS. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(11), 57-60.
4. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). THE ROLE OF THIOTRIAZOLINE IN THE ORGANISM. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 9(5), 152-155.
5. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). HEPTRAL IS USED IN LIVER DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 35(3), 76-78.
6. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). EFFECT OF TIVORTIN ON CARDIOMYOCYTE CELLS AND ITS ROLE IN MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 42, 255-257.
7. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). NEUROPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF CITICOLINE. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(1), 1-4.
8. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF TRIMETAZIDINE IN ISCHEMIC CARDIOMYOPATHY. *Journal of new century innovations*, 44(2), 3-8.
9. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ВСЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ ПРЕПАРАТА ИМУДОН. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 39-43.
10. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE EFFECT OF THE HEPARIN DRUG. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 34-38.
11. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF GLUCOCORTICOSTEROIDS IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 29-33.
12. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РОЛЬ ИНТЕЛЛАНОВОГО СИРОПА И ЦИАНОКОБАЛАМИНА В УЛУЧШЕНИИ ПАМЯТИ. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 44-48.
13. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). TREATMENT OF POLYNEUROPATHY WITH BERLITHION. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 201-209.

14. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF ASCORIL IN BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 191-200.
15. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG ARTOXAN. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 182-190.
16. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF RENGALIN IN CHRONIC BRONCHITIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 116-123.
17. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF ALMAGEL DRUG IN GASTRIC AND DUODENAL WOUND DISEASE. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 173-181.
18. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF CODELAK BRONCHO SYRUP IN CHILDREN'S PRACTICE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 109-115.
19. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE AEVIT DRUG EFFECT. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 124-132.
20. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF ALCHEBA DRUG IN POST-STROKE APHASIA. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 132-138.
21. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF HYALURON CHONDRON DRUG IN OSTEOARTHRITIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 139-145.
22. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT OF SIMETHICONE DROP IN FLATULENCE. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 95-101.
23. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). BENEFITS OF BETADINE SOLUTION. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 116-122.
24. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT INHALED GLUCOCORTICOIDS IN CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(1), 171-180.
25. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF VIGANTOL IN RICKETS. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 102-108.
26. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE VITAPROST DRUG RESULTS. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 109-115.
27. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF BIASEPTOL DRUG IN URINARY TRACT DISEASE. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 89-94.

28. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). PROPERTIES OF THE DRUG DORMIKIND. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 88-92.
29. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). IMMUNOMODULATORY FUNCTION OF DIBAZOL DRUG. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 83-87.
30. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). ADVANTAGES OF THE DRUG NERTRAL. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 98-101.
31. Эргашов, Б. К., & Ахмедов, Ш. Ж. (2024). ГИПЕРТОНИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ ЭТИОЛОГИЯ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 59-69.
32. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). HYPERTENSION, CLASSIFICATION AND PATHOGENESIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 50-58.
33. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIYASI. STENOKARDIYADA SHOSHILINCH TIBBIY YORDAM. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 12-20.
34. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). HYPERTENSION ETIOLOGY. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 32-41.
35. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). CARDIAC ISCHEMIA. ANGINA NURSING DIAGNOSIS AND CARE. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 44-52.
36. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). IMPORTANT INDICATIONS OF THE DRUG WOBENZYM. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 29-32.
37. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE RESULTS OF THE EFFECT OF THE DRUG VALIDOL. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 19-23.
38. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). VIFERON USE IN CHILDREN. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 24-28.
39. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF DUSPATALIN (MEBEVERINE HYDROCHLORIDE) IN GASTROINTESTINAL DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 93-97.
40. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ЭФФЕКТЫ СИРОПА ДЕПАКИНА (ВАЛЬПРОЕВАЯ КИСЛОТА). *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 148-152.

41. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG ALLOCHOL FOR CHRONIC CHOLECYSTITIS. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 133-137.
42. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). ВАЖНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА ПРЕПАРАТА ДЕ-НОЛ (субцитрат висмута). *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 143-147.
43. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). SPECIAL FEATURES OF BUDECTON DRUG. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 138-142.
44. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ЭФФЕКТИВНОЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ ПРЕПАРАТА КЕЙВЕР. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 137-143.
45. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USEFUL PROPERTIES OF THE DRUG YODOFOL. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 144-149.
46. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). FITOTERAPIYANING AKUSHER-GINEKOLOGIYADA ANAMIYATI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 121-125.
47. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG DOPROKIN. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 109-114.
48. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE EFFECT OF DOSTINEX ON THE BODY. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 115-120.
49. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ ПРЕПАРАТА КАНЕФРОН. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 138-143.
50. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ ПРЕПАРАТА ИНДОЛ. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 126-131.
51. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT OF ISMIZHEN DRUG ON BODY IMMUNITY. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 132-137.
52. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). POSITIVE EFFECTS OF THE DRUG CARCIL. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 127-131.
53. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ КАВИНТОНА. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 132-136.
54. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). Современный Эффект Спря Мометазон. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 62-65.
55. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF" SIMONTE PLUS" DRUG IN THE MODERN TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(5), 66-70.

56. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). FEATURES OF THE BIOMECHANISM OF THE DRUG LEVOMYCETIN (CHLORAMPHENICOL). *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(9), 298-301.
57. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE MOST IMPORTANT INDICATORS OF OMEGA 3 SUBSTANCE IN THE METABOLISM OF THE HUMAN BODY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(10), 113-117.
58. Komilovich, E. B., & Khalimovich, M. N. (2024). CARDIAC ISCHEMIA. ANGINA CLINICAL FORMS AND DIAGNOSIS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 70-78.
59. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). CORONARY HEART DISEASE. ANGINA EMERGENCY CARE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(7), 235-242.
60. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIK KASALLIGI. STENOKARDIYANI DAVOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY TAMOYILLARI. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 3-11.
61. Komilovich, E. B., & Khalimovich, M. N. (2024). DEPENDENCIES IN THE CLINIC AND DIAGNOSIS OF CORONARY HEART DISEASE AND ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 61-69.
62. Komilovich, E. B., & Xalimovich, M. N. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIYASIDA HAMSHIRALIK DIAGNOSTIKASI VA PARVARISHI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 79-85.
63. Komilovich, E. B., & Khalimovich, M. N. (2024). NURSING CARE FOR CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE, ANGINA PECTORIS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 86-94.
64. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE MOST IMPORTANT BENEFITS OF GINGER FOR THE HUMAN BODY'S IMMUNITY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(11), 269-273.
65. Ravshanovna, X. L. (2021, June). MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS OF TREATMENT OF DENTAL CARIES IN ADULTS. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" PLATFORM (pp. 118-119).
66. Xusenovich, M. S., & Turapjanovna, Z. M. (2024). SEMIZLIKNING TURLI FENOTIPLARDA KARDIOMETABOLIK XAVF OMILLARINI TAQQOSLASH. *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 7(4), 112-116.

67. Husenovich, M. S., & Turabdjanovna, Z. M. (2024). STUDY OF DIURNAL PROFILE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN DIFFERENT PHENOTYPE OBESITY. *образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире*, 43(1), 129-131.
68. Xusenovich, M. S. (2024, September). SEMIZLIKNI TURLI FENOTIPLARIDA YURAK QON-TOMIR KASALLIKLARINI KELIB CHIQISH XAVFI PROGNOZI. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 3, No. 26, pp. 15-18).
69. Xusenovich, M. S. (2024). O 'ZBEKISTONDA RESPUBLIKASIDA YURAK-QON TOMIR KASALLIKLARI TARQALISHI VA HOZIRGI KUNDAGI KO'RILAYOTGAN CHORA TADBIRLAR. *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE*, 2(3), 79-82.
70. Xusenovich, M. S., & Allayarovich, A. A. (2024). O 'ZBEKISTONDA YURAK-QON TOMIR KASALLIKLARI TARQALISHI VA HOZIRGI KUNDAGI TENDENSIYASI. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 4(38), 54-57.